

Sustainable
Erasmus+ Travel

Dossier on Recognition Mechanisms of Sustainable Travel for European Higher Education Institutions

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Table of abbreviations

CU	Charles University
DS	Diploma Supplement
EACEA	European Education and Culture Executive Agency
ECTS	European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System
EDC	European Digital Credentials for Learning
ESN	Erasmus Student Network
EUJ	European University Foundation
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IRO	International Relations Office/Officer
SET	Sustainable Erasmus+ Travel (project)
U.Porto	University of Porto
UZH	University of Zurich

1. Introduction

1.1 The SET project

The long-term aspiration of the [Sustainable Erasmus+ Travel \(SET\) project](#) is to **improve students' opportunities to adopt more environmentally sustainable habits during their mobility and to change their mindset towards viewing their trip to their mobility destination as a transformative experience in itself**. Since its implementation began in early 2024, we have researched the key features and factors behind students' transport choices for mobility, promoted the Erasmus+ mobility journey as an educational and transformative experience, and visualised the added value of green travel by developing a prototype to recognise green competencies. Overall, we reached more than 1.5M students and 500 higher education staff across Europe through coordinated communication and dissemination activities. The project is coordinated by the European University Foundation (EUF), whose consortium comprises three universities (Charles University, the University of Porto, and the University of Zurich), and the Erasmus Student Network (ESN). There are two student-led, volunteer-based organisations serving as associated partners: Erasmus by Train and Generation ClimateEurope.

Within the project's 4th Work Package, *Learning by Moving Green!*, we set out to increase self-awareness, promote learning outcomes in green mobility, clarify expectations, visualise its added value, and ultimately develop a prototype or potential options to recognise green competencies. The first was to determine the soft skills and competencies that students learned, acquired, and applied when travelling sustainably for their mobility, which were assessed through roundtable discussions with students (November–December 2024) and academics (November 2024–March 2025) who work on skills recognition and sustainability. These efforts led to the publication of the Green Competencies Repository in two formats: an interactive digital board game and its methodological report in PDF format.

1.2 Why a dossier on recognition of green competencies?

One of the core principles of the SET project has been to change the narrative to promote the **Erasmus+ mobility journey as an educational and transformative experience** that enables students to explore more European countries and celebrate European values to the fullest: human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law, and respect for human rights. Universities offer their students multiple opportunities to develop new skills and enhance existing ones in various settings. While formal learning materialises through structured educational frameworks and guided processes with predetermined learning outcomes, informal and non-formal learning usually takes place outside of education and training institutions and can also occur involuntarily. **Green travel in the context of Erasmus+ mobility exemplifies informal learning, thanks to its strong potential to foster and enhance a diverse range of competencies**. Even more so, according to a European Commission [Eurydice report](#), there is a growing willingness among higher education institutions (HEIs) to recognise skills acquired through non-formal and informal education.

The objective of this Dossier is to discuss possible **flexible and sustainable institutional mechanisms for quality assurance that acknowledge the enhancement of green competencies and validate students' choice to travel by low-carbon transport to reach and return from their mobility destination**. Concretely, we aim to:

- Recognise and appreciate Erasmus+ students' environmentally friendly behaviours and actionable commitments by travelling to and from their mobility destination using low-carbon means of transport.
- Help universities integrate environmental sustainability into their student mobility processes by presenting potential recognition pathways, along with a practical step-by-step guide, definitions, and recommendations for their implementation.

The document at hand presents a modular design for recognising green competencies in mobile students. We understand that European HEIs, including those in the SET consortium, have vastly different structures, processes, sizes, and realities when it comes to doing so. Therefore, the options presented below can be accommodated, tailored, or even combined by interested HEIs, depending on their preconditions. This also applies to the resources required to pilot the chosen mechanism(s), ranging from minimal effort to a maximalist approach.

In short, the purpose of this document is to highlight the cultural and behavioural shift that validating green competencies can unlock. This transformation can not only effectively increase the number of students opting for green travel when going on exchange abroad, but also contribute to delivering the green priority of Erasmus+ by “building the knowledge, skills, and attitudes on climate change and supporting sustainable development,” as included in the [Erasmus+ Programme Guide](#).

1.3 Target audience

This Dossier is, first and foremost, directed specifically to three target groups within the higher education ecosystem: leadership/senior management (such as Vice-Rectors for Internationalisation), International Relations/Erasmus+ Mobility officers, and academic coordinators. We anticipate that the findings and recommendations in this document will also resonate with Erasmus+ students, who are the core target group of the SET project, and the organisations/associations that represent them. Overall, because of the public nature of the deliverable, the intended audience and outreach within the European higher education community are expanding beyond the consortium level.

2. Methodology

The development of the Dossier included several steps. Firstly, in late 2025, U.Porto and the EUF prepared tailored guidelines and questions in order to collect feedback from staff members (7 in total) at the three partner universities. Their expertise was either in sustainability, accreditation, or internationalisation/international relations. The initial goal of using this validation method was to hold a single, mixed online roundtable with experts from all partner HEIs to discuss their proposed recognition solutions for the 16 green competencies identified in the [SET Repository](#) (See Appendix D).

However, it was challenging to find a suitable date that aligned with the schedules of all staff members at the universities (both academic and technical), so different methods for collecting this data were defined. Since the session was topic-based, the structure was adapted to request written feedback from the sustainability, internationalisation, and credit recognition experts at the University of Zurich (UZH) and Charles University (CU). The experts from these two institutions answered the questions and submitted comments to the repository in English via e-mail, liaising with the local SET project officers.

The University of Porto decided to keep the online format of the roundtable and organised a session with 3 staff members: two academics with experience as mobility coordinators, credit recognition and international projects involving micro and digital credentials and one researcher from CITTA – Research Centre for Territory, Transport and Environment at the Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto for the sustainability component. The interview was held on Zoom in Portuguese (the native language of the participants and the facilitator), and later transcribed and summarised to support this report.

Following this exercise, several rounds of internal brainstorming and conceptualisation deliberations took place in online meetings between colleagues from U.Porto and EUF. Thirdly, the first version of this dossier was presented to other project partners for a final round of internal feedback. Once all comments have been addressed and questions resolved, the dossier will be finalised and published on the [project website](#), the [EUF's Resource page](#), and the [Zenodo repository](#), ensuring long-term availability and visibility in the academic community.

3. Conceptual framework

3.1 Definition of “green travel” in the context of higher education mobility

In the context of the SET project, we have adopted the term “green travel,” which refers to ground and public travel, which is not the norm in student mobility. For instance, according to data from the [latest ESNsurvey XV edition](#), which was answered by 23.000 students, approximately 71% of respondents reported flying to their mobility destination. By contrast, green travel offers a more environmentally friendly, sometimes challenging, and responsible experience for students who take a proactive stance in preparing for and undertaking their mobility journey in this way. In addition, the [2026 Erasmus+ programme guide](#) provides a concrete definition in the Glossary: “Travel that uses low emissions means of transport for at least half of the round trip, such as bus, train, bike, or car-pooling. Traveling by boat will be considered as green travel if combined with other low-emissions means of transport.”

3.2 European competence-related frameworks for higher education

In the first half of 2024 we conducted an extensive desk research of several reference documents and reports, namely – LifeComp: The European Framework for Personal, Social and Learning to Learn Key Competence, GreenComp – The European sustainability competence framework, The Digital Competence Framework for Citizens, The European Qualifications Framework: supporting learning, work and cross-border mobility, and Green Skills and Knowledge Concepts: Labelling the ESCO classification. Secondly, to examine the link to employability, we reviewed two reports: the World Economic Forum's Future of Jobs Report 2023 and the OECD's Future of Education and Skills 2030. Another relevant source was the KA2 Erasmus Skills project, coordinated by the University Autónoma de Madrid, which developed a self-assessment tool for students to fully realise the learning outcomes of their mobility, as well as a methodology to support academics in integrating these outcomes into the curricula.

We adopted the definition of “competence” from the [Council Recommendation on key competences for lifelong learning](#), which describes it as “a dynamic combination of the knowledge, skills and attitudes”. Therefore, **competencies are an umbrella term encompassing not only specific expertise and information but also broader values, aspirations, priorities, and transversal capabilities owned by an individual.** Moreover, the [European Classification of Occupations, Skills and Competences](#) defines “green skills” as “The knowledge, abilities, values and attitudes needed to live in, develop and support a society which reduces the impact of human activity on the environment”.

3.3 The SET Green Competencies Repository

Our previous desk [research](#) concluded with an overview of the complementary transversal competencies that could be unlocked and reinforced by green travel (see Appendix D). We deliberated on their realistic potential for development through real-world scenarios that encompass the entire green travel experience, from booking the itinerary to travelling on board to actively embodying an environmentally-conscious attitude towards the planet, and more. After the initial identification of 19

competencies, two online roundtables were conducted with Erasmus+ students who had previous green travel experience to validate them. These discussions led to the refinement, clarification, and merging of some of them, and the [final repository](#) with 16 competencies was published in August 2025. In short, our research showed that there is **immense potential for exchange students to further develop their sustainable practices, strengthen different and correlative transversal competencies for personal growth, and contribute to social cohesion and interconnectedness in Europe, all before they even reach their destination!**

4. Recognition mechanisms for green travel

Universities increasingly recognise that sustainable travel can foster meaningful learning beyond the formal education and other opportunities they already provide. There is a growing correlation between green travel and areas such as adaptability, planning, environmental responsibility, intercultural awareness, and critical thinking. These competencies are real, valuable, and often under-recognised in nonformal and informal settings unless institutions strategically create opportunities for students to reflect on and articulate them.

This section draws on content collected from expert and student roundtables at three partner institutions in the SET project, which share a common understanding that potential **recognition should be flexible, credible, and centred on student reflection**, while avoiding overly rigid or bureaucratic systems. Overall, UZH colleagues emphasised that students should be the narrators of their own learning rather than institutions acting as gatekeepers. CU experts stressed the need for clear learning outcomes and structured reflection to ensure meaningful recognition, whereas U.Porto staff proposed both reflective tools and formal academic pathways, including ECTS-based short modules.

To reflect these different views, this guide discusses four recognition mechanisms from less to more formal ways of assessing competencies gained with sustainable travel:

- **Self-assessment questionnaire**: a student-centred tool, designed for a more informal self-evaluation by the students.
- **Certificates and digital credentials**: a dematerialised and flexible format that is being used in multiple employability platforms.
- **Diploma Supplement**: a “label” or “mention” of informal learning attached to the diploma.
- **Academic recognition through ECTS**: a more structured format that foresees the development of a unit course or module for HEIs seeking deeper strategic integration.

If a university chooses one of these mechanisms, it can be used independently or combined. **Together, they offer a scalable continuum: from simple reflection to formal academic credit.** This allows HEIs with different approaches, interests, levels of administrative flexibility, autonomy, and readiness to adopt the model that best fits their context.

4.1 Self-assessment questionnaire

A self-assessment questionnaire is a structured reflective tool that guides students in identifying the skills, attitudes, and knowledge they applied or strengthened during their sustainable travel experience. The proposed format aligns with the competencies in the SET Green Competencies Repository and invites students to evaluate their perceived learning using statements and short reflective prompts. UZH experts viewed “a student self-reflection report completed before and after the mobility period” as a credible, low-risk method for recognising learning. U.Porto similarly recommended “the development of a

competence self-assessment questionnaire” to support evaluation and data collection. A template is attached in Appendix A below.

This format has a number of advantages, such as the **simplicity of the procedure, scalability, strong institutional suitability and lighter administrative burden**. This option also empowers students to articulate their learning and consciously recognise their own gains from green travel, supports behavioural awareness and personal growth, and aligns with the student view that emerged during the student roundtables held by U.Porto and the EUF in late 2024 that green travel is an iterative process of learning. Finally, a self-assessment questionnaire may also provide a foundation for more formal recognition mechanisms (such as certificates, Diploma Supplement mentions, or ECTS modules that are explored next). In sum, this mechanism might fit HEIs with, for instance, limited or no existing recognition structures for non-formal and informal learning opportunities, as well as institutions wishing to promote self-reflection among their students without committing to formal certification.

Structure of the questionnaire

The questionnaire is designed as a reflective tool that guides students through a structured analysis of their sustainable travel experience. Rather than presenting isolated questions, it invites students to engage with a series of “Yes,” “No,” or “N/A” affirmation statements that mirror the 16 competencies in the Green Competencies Repository. These statements encourage students to consider whether they applied or strengthened particular competencies during their journey, for example, recognising moments when they used planning skills to manage complex itineraries or relied on adaptability to respond to unexpected changes. This questionnaire should be completed only once at the end of the mobility and sustainable travel experience to allow them time to reflect on all the competencies they have enhanced. These components help students express their learning in a clear, structured, and meaningful way.

Evaluation method

The evaluation process for this questionnaire is intentionally self-directed and student-centred. Students complete it independently, without the need for guidance, grading, external validation, or formal assessment. The purpose is not to judge performance, but to support awareness, reflection, and personal growth. As an optional second step, once completed, the questionnaire can serve as valuable evidence for the HEI to integrate into a deeper process to advance formal recognition, such as in the ways described below. The results of the questionnaire can, if possible and desired, be included in a certificate or in an entry in the Diploma Supplement, but its primary function remains reflective and limited to students’ knowledge.

Administrative procedure

The self-assessment questionnaire can be hosted online (e.g. on institutional forms or sent via email) and made readily available to exchange students, so they can complete it at their convenience and reflect on the competencies identified in this sheet. In its essence, it is not an official institutional document, but it can be tailored to include, for instance, the logo of the university, if needed. Optionally, the student can return the completed questionnaire to either the mobility or sustainability officer for reporting, internal

monitoring, or follow-up. In the case of CU, for instance, after returning from their mobility programme, students complete the mandatory questionnaire for the European Commission, and a voluntary one for their "Charles Abroad" platform.

4.2 Certificates and Digital Credentials

HEIs might decide to use certificates and digital credentials issued by trusted external platforms or by the institutions themselves to formally acknowledge a student's engagement in sustainable travel and the associated competencies. They could be issued in various formats depending on institutional capacity. There are two main types of certificates, both of which require evidence of achievement:

- Certificate of Participation: Confirms that the student undertook sustainable travel.
- Certificate of Achievement (more specific): Recognises demonstrated competencies (indicates a list of competencies gained).

U.Porto highlights the ProSkills Project as a good practice: a certification programme for extracurricular experiences intended for all bachelor's and master's degree students at the School of Economics, which awards 3 ECTS for transversal skills demonstrated through student-led activities. The Pro-Skills initiative aims to formally acknowledge each student's developmental journey throughout their degree, showcasing the transversal competencies they have acquired and reinforcing the comprehensiveness of the School of Economics' preparation of its graduates for the labour market, thereby strengthening the recognised quality of its graduates. This way, they will hold not only an academic degree but also a complementary certificate of experiences and skills that is recognised by employers as an essential component of their professional profile. Although not specific to sustainability, it provides a strong model for structured recognition. For more information on how it works, check the [Pro-Skills website](#).

Digital credentials and micro-credentials

The definition and principles of micro-credentials are defined in the [2022 Council Recommendation on a European approach to micro-credentials for lifelong learning and employability](#). Concretely, they can be issued based on formal, informal and non-formal learning. The validation of non-formal and informal learning can also happen "on the basis of assessment of learning outcomes resulting from non-formal and informal learning." There is a unique and clear opportunity for digital credentials to offer HEIs a flexible way to acknowledge students' sustainable travel experiences in a format that is both portable and widely recognised by employers. Instead of relying solely on traditional paper certificates, institutions can issue credentials such as Open Badges, LinkedIn-compatible badges, or European Digital Credentials for Learning (EDC). These formats allow students to showcase their competencies directly on professional platforms and in their CVs. U.Porto already makes use of EDCs and digital badges to connect learners with employers, illustrating how these tools can be integrated into existing institutional practices.

To ensure that these credentials carry meaning and credibility, HEIs may ask students to provide evidence of their sustainable travel choices. This would include, for example, travel tickets and, depending on the respective institutional requirements and practices, itineraries, carbon-saving calculations, or a

declaration of honour. This could be combined with the self-assessment questionnaire or a short reflective report to place greater emphasis on, and raise awareness of, the competencies practised. These elements help ground the credential in concrete outcomes and reflective learning.

Evaluation method

The evaluation process for awarding a digital credential is based on simple evidence, for e.g. a proof of sustainable travel, usually easy to track for those who ask for the green top-up/travel support, and/or a pre-defined task (not something academic as it will be “evaluated” by technical staff). This should be designed to require the least extra work for staff members, whether from mobility offices, sustainability teams, or academic departments. Here, one would need to consider how to minimise the workload of both staff and students and how to simplify the monitoring of green travel as much as possible. Also, this would need to be defined in advance and presented to students at the time of application (for an Erasmus exchange, within the Green Mobility Aspects), in line with the standard requirements of HEIs for granting green travel support. Detailed grading is neither necessary nor recommended. The emphasis would remain on recognising meaningful engagement rather than assessing performance in a formal academic sense.

Administrative procedure

The administrative process for issuing certificates and digital credentials is intentionally straightforward, ensuring that recognition remains accessible for both students and institutions. Once a student has met the criteria, certificates could be generated through the institution’s potentially already existing systems, following the same procedures used for other forms of extracurricular or skills-based recognition. The institution can, for instance, either issue a certificate or digital badge automatically when the student applies for an Erasmus+ exchange, or purchase a license for digital credentials from an external provider, such as Open Badges or European Digital Credentials for Learning. They are issued through the institution’s chosen badge or credential platform, allowing students to store and share them easily across professional networks. Alternatively, institutions may choose to record the credential in the student’s file or academic record, although this step is optional and depends on internal policy and capacity.

4.3 Diploma Supplement

According to the [2026 Erasmus+ programme guide](#), a diploma supplement (DS) is defined as “An annex to the official qualification documentation, which is designed to provide more detailed information on the studies completed according to an agreed format, which is internationally recognised; a document accompanying a higher education diploma”. As such, it can document formal, non-formal, and informal learning undertaken during a student’s higher education degree, though its implementation and signing vary significantly across countries and institutions. Some SET partners currently use the DS to record volunteering, participation in Blended Intensive Programmes (BIPs), Erasmus internships or extracurricular activities. In such cases, sustainability-related experiences may well be incorporated if there are existing institutional guidelines or policies to follow.

Documentation

HEIs may decide to document sustainable travel undertaken within the framework of Erasmus+ mobility by formally recording students' use of low-emission transport options, their active engagement in planning environmentally responsible travel solutions for the mobility destination (e.g., presenting carbon footprint calculations for different transport options), and their participation in structured reflection activities. In some cases, this documentation may include the achievement of a digital credential linked to green competencies, providing an additional layer of formal recognition. Together, these elements allow the evaluators to select whether the "mention" in the DS describes not only what the student did, but also how they reflected on and applied sustainability competencies.

Recommended wording

DS entries may be phrased to reflect both the action undertaken and the competencies demonstrated. Institutions could register a mention that a student undertook an Erasmus+ mobility using environmentally sustainable transport modes, evidencing planning, resilience and environmental awareness and engaged in structured reflection on sustainable mobility practices in this context. Under the mention of "Green Mobility," HEIs can invite students to add an explanation of which aspects and competencies were fostered. Optionally, universities can combine this measure with the results of the self-assessment questionnaire or a more formal evaluation.

Relevant DS categories

Such information may be appropriately included under sections relating to "Additional Information," "Non-formal and Informal Learning," "Transversal Skills," or "Participation in Sustainability Initiatives," depending on the structure adopted by the issuing institution. Please find in Appendix C examples from the U.Porto (the screenshot below) and CU that mention non-formal learning.

Evaluation method

The evaluation required for this form of recognition is intentionally simplified and based on documentation currently being collected or submitted through mobility management processes. Institutions could verify basic evidence, such as travel documentation or proof of travel, access to green travel support, and even the results of the self-assessment questionnaire. The inclusion of the latter would strengthen the justification of actually fostering the said competencies. The purpose of this evaluation is not to assess academic performance, but rather to acknowledge participation and choice. This approach ensures

that sustainable travel could be formally recognised while remaining accessible and administratively feasible for institutions.

Administrative procedure

Taking the procedures established by U.Porto as an example, the inclusion of a DS mention should be authorised by the competent body, such as the Rector or an equivalent University authority. In other universities, the DS can be signed by the study programme coordinator, the national Rectorate or an IRO. An academic committee supported by officers working on recognition issues should also approve standardised wording and establish clear eligibility criteria. To ensure fairness and consistency across faculties, HEIs are encouraged to adopt templates that describe the competences achieved through a green travel experience.

To ensure transparency and accessibility, if an HEI selects this approach, it would be advisable to publish precise guidelines for students that detail all aspects of the recognition process. These guidelines should outline the eligibility criteria, specify the documentation required for validation, indicate any application deadlines if the process is request-based, and identify the points of contact for questions or support. Depending on institutional policy, the inclusion of informal or non-formal learning mentioned in the DS may occur automatically upon validation completion, or may require the student to submit a formal request. Communication at this stage helps students understand the process and ensures equitable access to recognition. Once validated, the mention should be recorded in the student information system and automatically included in Section 6 (“Additional Information”) of the Diploma Supplement, in line with the European Commission / Council of Europe / UNESCO model.

At the University of Porto, the possibility of adding an initiative to the list of complementary activities eligible for mention in the Diploma Supplement is based on a substantiated proposal submitted by one of the Faculties. This proposal should outline the value and merit of the activity for the student’s academic journey, as well as its scientific and pedagogical relevance. The Office for Academic Organisation and Development (FOA) is responsible for the technical verification that the activity meets the requirements and criteria established for activities eligible for inclusion in the Diploma Supplement, with final approval granted by the Rector. At the institutional level, it is also possible to recognise a given activity or initiative based on its alignment with the University’s mission and values. The University of Porto’s Volunteering Programme is an example of this approach. In this case, the Volunteering Committee is responsible for determining which volunteering activities and projects may be eligible for mention in the Diploma Supplement. For an Erasmus+ Sustainable Travel, a committee should include members, e.g., from the International Office and the Sustainability Office.

4.4 Academic Recognition through ECTS

Recognition through ECTS is the most formal mechanism. In line with this approach, experts from U.Porto proposed developing a dedicated curricular unit or module on sustainable mobility, designed to provide a structured academic framework for the green travel experience. The workload for the module

would be around 1.5 ECTS credits, calculated according to the standard European ECTS methodology, in which 1 ECTS corresponds to approximately 25-30 hours of student effort, including preparation, online participation, and assessment. The module could be delivered online or in person prior to students' departure for their Erasmus+ mobility and be included in their Learning Agreement. Its content can be developed and taught collaboratively by academic staff from 1 and more European Higher Education Institutions, ensuring both institutional international cooperation and an innovative pedagogical content and methods.

Structure of the curricular unit

The following section gives an example of how such a curricular unit might be designed as a structured learning pathway, with planning as the main competency to be developed through project-based learning and objective tasks. It involves three components: preparing student travel (e.g. calculating emissions using online calculators and other tools), reflection, and a final report. The first component of the unit course would be a pre-departure module of approximately 12 hours, introducing students to the principles of sustainable mobility and carbon-footprint literacy, while equipping them with the practical skills and knowledge required to plan complex, lower-emission itineraries in order to choose more sustainable modes of transport. The module could also develop critical awareness by identifying greenwashing practices by companies, brands, or organisations and by exploring the social and cultural dimensions of sustainable travel, integrating the Sustainable Development Goals.

The second component takes place during the mobility period, when students are invited to maintain a reflective diary in which they monitor and analyse their behaviours in areas such as transport, food consumption, heating and other carbon-related choices, following the guidance proposed by U.Porto. This ongoing reflection encourages conscious decision-making and links theoretical knowledge with lived experience.

The unit concludes with a final report in which students critically justify their travel decisions, reflect on the challenges encountered, and articulate the transversal and sustainability-related competencies developed throughout the process.

Inclusivity and equity

To ensure fairness and access, the curricular unit recognises that sustainable travel is not equally feasible for all students, particularly where geographical constraints limit realistic alternatives to air travel. Moreover, there are economic barriers as travelling sustainably is not financially accessible to every student (depending on the destination). For this reason, undertaking a fully sustainable journey should not constitute a mandatory requirement to fulfil the goals of this unit course. Instead, the academic focus may rest on the student's capacity to design and justify a sustainable travel plan, therefore simulating the steps and skills needed to realise a green trip, and ensuring that learning outcomes can be achieved even where practical implementation, because of health, personal, financial or other reasons, is not possible.

Interinstitutional cooperation

For online modules, the initiative lends itself to collaboration among HEIs, which may co-design shared modules, use virtual learning environments, and exchange teaching materials and expertise. Such cooperation enhances scalability and ensures the long-term sustainability of the project. This collaborative approach is aligned with established frameworks for shared curricular provision, fostering consistency and mutual recognition across institutions.

At the University of Porto, for unit courses offered in partnership with other institutions, the administrative headquarters must always be a U.Porto faculty/school, corresponding to the faculty/school whose scientific competences cover the main focus of the training. If the training involves only U.Porto units, full collaborations require signatures from the Management and Scientific Council/Committee of each participating faculty, while collaborations based solely on teaching staff participation require authorisation from the Deans of all contributing faculties except the headquarters. When external institutions are involved, a formal partnership agreement must be signed by the participating U.Porto faculty and the external partners, and approved by the Rector. This process ensures clear allocation of responsibilities, regulatory compliance, and proper institutional oversight.

Evaluation method

The evaluation of the “Sustainable Travel” module could be designed to reflect the learning outcomes and competencies outlined in the SET project’s repository of green competencies. Rather than focusing on numerical grades, assessment follows a qualitative Pass/Fail approach, recognising students’ engagement, critical reflection, and application of sustainable practices in the context of their mobility abroad. The evaluation aims to capture both the knowledge and the transversal competencies acquired, including environmental awareness, planning and adaptability, responsible decision-making, and the ability to assess and reduce personal carbon impact.

Students demonstrate their learning through a range of evidence, which may include travel logs, carbon footprint calculations, reflective journals, photographs, field notes, and records of participation in other environmental initiatives or practices linked to their green travel. To consolidate their learning and encourage the practical application of skills, students may also complete a final integrative project, such as a proposal to enhance campus mobility or promote sustainable travel practices at their host institution. Evaluation could be carried out by sustainability specialists, with appropriate academic oversight, to ensure the assessment is rigorous, coherent, and aligned with the module’s intended learning outcomes.

Administrative procedure

To explain the process of creating, internally accrediting, and recognising an online learning module, we will use the example of the Academic Services of the University of Porto (U.Porto) that follows a clear set of procedures designed to ensure academic quality and regulatory compliance. The development of a distance-learning Continuous Education module at U.Porto is proposed by the academic staff of the faculty leading the initiative. This academic personnel has to complete the required forms, providing

information on the module's content, learning outcomes, and pedagogical relevance. The forms are first reviewed and accredited internally by the competent bodies of the proposing staff's respective home faculty, then submitted to the Rector via the Office for Academic Organisation and Development (FOA) for verification before ECTS definition. ECTS are assigned according to U.Porto regulations, with 1 ECTS corresponding to approximately 27 hours of total student workload, including contact hours (in-person or synchronous online sessions, tutorials, labs, or fieldwork) and independent study (projects, assessment preparation, research, or asynchronous online activities). Modules may be credited in multiples of 0.5 ECTS once the minimum of 1 ECTS is achieved. Contact hours should generally represent 25–35% of the total workload unless justified otherwise.¹

At U.Porto, modules can be delivered entirely online, using synchronous and/or asynchronous learning. Assessment should preferably be continuous and distributed, but where exams are required, they can be conducted either in person or remotely using validated digital platforms that ensure security, reliability, and academic integrity. All students must follow the same assessment method, and remote exams should be monitored with cameras and microphones to uphold integrity, while in-person exams are supervised by qualified staff or partner premises.

¹ According to U.Porto regulations, 1 ECTS corresponds to approximately 27 hours of total student workload, including contact hours and independent study. Credits may be increased in increments of 0.5 ECTS once the minimum of 1 ECTS is reached. Contact hours (e.g., classes, tutorials, fieldwork, synchronous online sessions and assessment time) should normally represent 25–35% of the total workload. Independent study includes project work, preparation for assessment, individual research and asynchronous online learning.

5. Quality assurance, inclusion and ethical considerations

To ensure academic integrity, the recognition of green travel choices should uphold the reliability of existing institutional, academic, and administrative processes. To achieve this, institutions that decide to informally or formally acknowledge potential competencies acquired through green mobility should establish **clear and transparent procedures aligned with their internal quality assurance mechanisms**.

If the institution opts to provide recognition of green travel through an academic component, such as an ECTS-awarding module as discussed earlier, the academic content, learning outcomes, and assessment methods should meet the same quality requirements as those applied to any other curricular unit. This involves designing learning outcomes that are coherent with the purpose, ensuring that teaching materials and activities are pedagogically sound, and applying assessment criteria that are transparent, fair, and aligned with the intended outcomes. Depending on the national legislation or internal regulations, formal accreditation might be required, and internal quality assurance mechanisms should be used to verify that the module maintains academic quality and that student performance is evaluated consistently and appropriately.

At the same time, planning recognition would involve **defining explicit and publicly accessible criteria for what is an eligible green travel choice and ensuring that these criteria are applied consistently across faculties and mobility offices**.

The potential recognition criteria should be embedded within existing quality assurance cycles, including administrative audits or periodic reviews of mobility processes, and staff should be adequately trained to apply the criteria and verify documentation in a consistent and transparent manner. Maintaining clear records of recognition decisions further supports traceability and institutional accountability. By integrating these elements into established quality assurance structures, institutions would ensure that green travel recognition remains credible, coherent, and aligned with broader standards governing academic and administrative integrity within the European Higher Education Area.

On the other hand, this Dossier and the potential recognition pathways should not reinforce inequities among students with different mobility opportunities. According to data collected from sustainability experts, **recognition practices should be designed to avoid disadvantaging students whose geographical location, transport availability, or financial circumstances limit their ability to choose low-carbon travel options**. For example, students living in peripheral or remote regions may face significantly higher costs or longer travel times when attempting to travel sustainably, compared with students based in central Europe with extensive rail networks. Institutions could therefore adopt criteria that consider the most feasible sustainable option available to each student, rather than applying uniform criteria that may inadvertently create inequities. Green travel should not be mandatory to access the opportunity for green competency recognition via the course unit; its focus should be on the pre-departure planning stage (e.g., calculating carbon emissions, proposing sustainable transport options) rather than on the travel itself.

6. Recommendations

6.1 Recommendations for HEIs to recognise green travel

This section is dedicated to practical recommendations to guide HEIs seeking to adopt and implement one of the green travel recognition mechanisms. The aim is to translate the solutions presented in this Dossier into clear, actionable steps that can be integrated into institutional internationalisation strategies and mobility procedures. The following steps outline a proposed roadmap for universities planning to integrate one or more recognition mechanisms for sustainable travel choices into the exchange-abroad experience and its associated learning outcomes.

a) High-level support for green travel recognition

At the central level, it would be advisable for green travel to be designated as a strategic priority for internationalisation and incorporated into their sustainability strategies and internationalisation policies. Green travel should be acknowledged as a success factor for not only effectively reducing the carbon footprint of internationalisation, but also for the development of transversal competencies. A designated working group, comprising, for example, representatives from the International Office, Sustainability Office, and Academic Affairs, can develop guidelines that explain and endorse the recognition of sustainable mobility within the different local units (faculties, departments or schools) and oversee the development, implementation, and evaluation of the administrative recognition procedures. It is at the University's discretion to facilitate conversations and dialogue among faculties and to allocate roles.

b) Define the scope and objectives

The working group selected to develop centralised recognition tools for sustainable mobility should define what is understood institutionally as “green travel” and which types of mobility activities and modes of transport are eligible for green recognition (e.g., semester mobility, short-term mobility, blended mobility, field trips). In this regard, HEIs are encouraged to adopt the definition laid out in the [latest Erasmus+ programme guide](#): *“Travel that uses low emissions means of transport for at least half of the round trip, such as bus, train, bike, or car-pooling. Traveling by boat will be considered as green travel if combined with other low-emissions means of transport.”* Furthermore, clarity is needed on whether recognition focuses on sustainable travel to/from the mobility destination, on sustainable travel behaviours acquired during the mobility experience, or on both.

c) Select appropriate recognition mechanisms

Depending on institutional priorities and administrative capacity, HEIs may adopt one or more of the following mechanisms, listed below in ascending order of institutional and academic formality. These should be coherent with existing institutional recognition practices for non-formal or informal learning:

- Student self-assessment questionnaire.
- Institutional certificates, digital open badges, or digital credentials.

- Label/mention in the Diploma Supplement.
- ECTS awarding modules focused on sustainability and green travel competencies (suggested to be online and offered in cooperation with other European institutions).

d) Define learning outcomes and evaluation methods

Learning outcomes should be aligned with relevant European competence frameworks, such as [GreenComp: the European sustainability competence framework](#), or [Green Skills and Knowledge Concepts: Labelling the ESCO classification](#). The SET Green Competences repository can support the recognition process by gathering information from diverse European competence frameworks across different fields, including multiple dimensions of competence (not only environmental). The institution should also specify the types of evidence students must provide to initiate the green travel recognition process (e.g., travel documentation, carbon footprint calculations, reflective assignments, pictures, booking confirmation) and develop transparent assessment criteria to ensure fairness and academic integrity.

e) Integrate green travel recognition into existing processes

It is recommended that the selected recognition pathway be incorporated into established mobility procedures to ensure consistency, streamline processes, and improve operational efficiency; for instance, this involves pre-departure and orientation briefings, travel documentation processes, and post-mobility reporting, as well as the dissemination of financial incentives, such as the green travel support and top-ups, if available. If the chosen recognition option is a certificate or a mention in DS, staff involved in mobility management and academic recognition should receive appropriate training to ensure accurate verification of green travel choices and consistent application of recognition criteria. In the case of CU, for example, this would need to be addressed at the central administration in consultation with all the international offices of the 17 faculties, as well as with other departments at the Rectorate. Alternatively, for the participation in a specific ECTS-awarding module, academic staff from different study fields (e.g., environmental engineering, economics, environmental and sustainability studies) should be involved in the co-design and delivery of the course.

f) Dissemination of green travel recognition to students

Clear and timely communication is essential to ensure that students are aware of the availability, learning outcomes, and value of green travel recognition. Institutions should disseminate information through preparatory mobility sessions, updated and accessible institutional websites and official materials, student portals, or other tailored advisory services. The role of IROs, mobility officers, and Erasmus+ coordinators is crucial, as they have direct access and a legitimate function to best inform outgoing students about their expected commitments, leading to the recognition of their green competencies. Communication should focus on explaining the recognition process implemented at the home institution, the eligibility criteria, and the benefits of choosing low-carbon travel options, including increased visibility for environmentally responsible choices and potential enhancements to students' academic and professional

profiles. Ultimately, consistent and positive messaging can help normalise green travel as a valuable and encouraged mode of mobility.

g) Monitoring the implementation and impact of green travel recognition

It is recommended that institutions establish mechanisms to monitor the implementation and impact of the green travel recognition method(s) they have adopted. This may include collecting data on the number of students opting for green travel support, the types of travel modes used, and qualitative student feedback on the recognition process. The office or staff responsible for this task should be those who already have direct outreach to students and access to this kind of data, notably IROs or sustainability officers, whose collaboration would bring significant value and create synergies between mobility and environmental sustainability. Regular evaluation, in accordance with existing internal protocols, will support continuous improvement, ensuring that the recognition mechanism remains relevant, efficient, and aligned with institutional priorities. Lastly, sharing outcomes, lessons learned, and good practices within both official and informal national and pan-European networks, such as, but not limited to, European Universities Alliances and Councils of Rectors, can contribute to sector-wide support for developing and streamlining coherent approaches across the European Higher Education Area.

6.2 Policy recommendations for European-level stakeholders

To achieve large-scale adoption of these recognition methods, European decision-makers, notably the European Commission and the National Agencies of Erasmus+, are invited to support, encourage, and guide HEIs in recognising and validating the development of students' green competencies. European decision makers may consider integrating new recommendations into the Erasmus+ Programme Guide on the development of recognition standards for green travel. The following suggestions address organisations involved in recognition, mobility, and competence frameworks:

- **Develop a European framework for recognising green travel choices:** A shared framework would support coherence, common definitions, streamlining, and transparency across institutions, helping to standardise recognition practices within the European Higher Education Area.
- **Provide guidance on the use of recognition mechanisms:** Offer straightforward recommendations on how institutions may formally recognise green travel competencies, and mainstream available options to support consistent implementation across Europe. It would also be important to provide templates and detailed guidelines for administrative procedures on issuing certificates, digital credentials, or Diploma Supplement entries.
- **Introduce the recognition of transversal competencies fostered through green travel in the Erasmus+ Programme Guide, the European Charter for Higher Education and the Erasmus+ Student Charter:** Complementing the green travel support and reinforcing the programme's commitment to low-carbon mobility by scaling up efforts to promote and validate the development of green competencies through informal learning.
- **Support cross-border collaboration and capacity-building:** Funding for pilot projects, communities of practice, and knowledge-sharing platforms, such as the cross-sectoral [Education for](#)

[Climate coalition](#), would help to accelerate the dissemination of robust recognition practices and foster streamlining across education sectors. The role of and collaboration with the [Salto Green Resource Center](#) could be a catalyst for unlocking this potential for a spillover effect across sectors, educational institutions, and countries, as well as for ensuring the sustainability of results.

7. Conclusion

One of the key objectives of the SET project has been to help change the narrative around mobility and sustainable travel. In other words, **we aimed to promote the Erasmus+ journey to and from the mobility destination as an educational and transformative experience that enables students to explore more countries, cultures, languages, and landscapes, and celebrate European values and interconnectedness to the fullest.** We reiterate that green travel, in the context of Erasmus+ exchanges abroad, is an example of informal learning, owing to its strong potential to foster and enhance a diverse set of competencies. These competencies range from adaptability and planning to critical thinking, environmental values, and digital skills; all of these are critical in today's polycrisis societies. Universities, as official education, learning, and training institutions, are encouraged to recognise the complete body of knowledge, skills, and internationalisation experiences students accumulate throughout their academic itineraries.

The Dossier at hand serves as a flexible institutional guide for quality assurance in recognition matters that reward students' choice to travel by low-carbon transport to/from their mobility destination. Based on the SET project research/data collection, we discussed **four recognition mechanisms for assessing transversal competencies enhanced through sustainable travel:** a student self-assessment questionnaire, digital certificates and credentials, a mention in the Diploma Supplement, and an ECTS-awarding module. These mechanisms could be used independently or in combination, offering a scalable continuum from simple reflection to formal academic credit.

Ultimately, the main goal of this document is, more than finding specific answers to encourage recognition of sustainable travel, **to provide concrete options and inspire institutions to reflect more deeply on this topic that matters to students and can impact mobility in Europe positively within the Erasmus+ Programme.** In addition to financial incentives, the programme should promote recognition of the experience of choosing to travel sustainably. This recognition should be developed both as an institutional strategy to reduce carbon emissions in Europe and the European Union, particularly those resulting from frequent and often unnecessary short-haul flights within Europe, and as an academic strategy to equip students with competencies in areas such as planning, environmental awareness, and responsible decision-making, which are essential for becoming critically informed and globally engaged citizens.

Regardless of their age, study level, field, or other factors, **all mobile students who adopt responsible, eco-conscious behaviours by travelling sustainably to/from their host city should be supported, celebrated, and acknowledged.** The scale-up and combination of all their individual choices are concrete indicators that the Erasmus+ programme can be made "greener" thanks to the effective reduction of travel-related greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions on a large scale. This is in line with the horizontal programme priority on the environment and the fight against climate change, as well as the Erasmus Charter for Higher Education 2021-2027 (ECHE).

HOW TO COMPLETE THE SET PROJECT'S SELF-ASSESSMENT SHEET

WHAT IS IT? This self-assessment questionnaire is designed to evaluate the enhancement and application of competencies (skills, knowledge, and attitudes) through sustainable travel. The SET green competences repository is available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/13768041>.

WHY SHOULD YOU ANSWER IT? To gain a deeper understanding, exact vocabulary, and ownership of the complementary skills, attitudes, and knowledge you applied or strengthened during your sustainable travel.

WHO SHOULD ANSWER IT? Erasmus+ higher education students who **travelled with a sustainable mode of transport to/from their mobility destination** either for studies or a traineeship (i.e., by train, bus, bike, carpooling, boat, or a combination of low-emission modes).

HOW TO ANSWER IT? For each of the following 16 competencies, read the short statements carefully and answer in the right column to confirm or reject your agreement with it. If a statement does not apply to your experience, write "N/A".

WHEN SHOULD YOU FILL IT? After completing your exchange period and returning to your home city.

1. EMOTIONAL REGULATION

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I am able to recognise my emotions and self-regulate.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I can cope with stressful and unexpected situations that can arise in green travel.	<input type="checkbox"/>

2. SELF-MOTIVATION

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I can undertake complex and demanding tasks.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I can maintain a positive attitude on a longer, more adventurous green journey.	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. PLANNING

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I know how to plan a trip using only sustainable modes of transport.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I manage my time efficiently.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I can anticipate the costs of my green journey and build/guarantee my budget in advance.	<input type="checkbox"/>

4. RESPONSIBILITY

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I can reliably fulfil obligations with integrity and proactiveness.	<input type="checkbox"/>

I can organise a safe and feasible green trip.	<input type="checkbox"/>
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5. CURIOSITY

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I have a curious attitude towards new situations.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am interested in unique and diverse experiences, thanks to green travel.	<input type="checkbox"/>

6. ENVIRONMENTAL VALUES

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I am aware of climate change and the environmental impact of travel/transportation.	<input type="checkbox"/>
My actions align with my environmental principles.	<input type="checkbox"/>

7. INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I can interpret information through verbal and non-verbal communication.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I feel comfortable expressing myself and engaging with others in my native tongue.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I feel comfortable expressing myself and engaging with others in a foreign language.	<input type="checkbox"/>

8. INTERCULTURAL AWARENESS

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I enjoy being immersed in new cultural environments and engaging with the local community along the way/during my stopovers.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I appreciate having direct contact with other cultures, traditions, practices, and mentalities.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I developed a greater respect for the cultural diversity I encountered during my green journey.	<input type="checkbox"/>

9. EUROPEAN VALUES

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I believe sustainable travel makes me more aware of European values.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I appreciate the EU's freedom of movement in the Schengen Area.	<input type="checkbox"/>

10. INDIVIDUAL INITIATIVE

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I can proactively promote sustainable travel.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I feel confident about pursuing green travel in the future.	<input type="checkbox"/>

11. ONLINE SEARCH

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I can resort to online platforms, apps, and websites to research information on green travel.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I remain updated about the latest news and receive notifications about my green journey.	<input type="checkbox"/>

12. EVALUATING DATA, INFORMATION AND DIGITAL CONTENT

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I know how to assess the validity/credibility of information online.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am able to explore new ways to search for and exchange information online.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am able to identify greenwashing practices.	<input type="checkbox"/>

13. CRITICAL THINKING

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I am able to make an informed judgment.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I can challenge preconceived notions around green travel and Erasmus+/mobility programmes.	<input type="checkbox"/>

14. ADAPTABILITY/FLEXIBILITY

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I can adapt to new circumstances during my green journey.	<input type="checkbox"/>

15. EVALUATE THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF PERSONAL BEHAVIOUR

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I can critically reflect on the different dimensions of my lifestyle and its impact on the natural environment.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that different modes of transport have varying carbon footprints.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am aware of the potential for green travel to have spillover effects in other aspects of lifestyle, such as food, clothing, and waste management.	<input type="checkbox"/>

16. ADOPT WAYS TO REDUCE THE NEGATIVE IMPACT OF CONSUMPTION

STATEMENT	YES, NO, N/A
I can make responsible, eco-conscious decisions to reduce the harmful environmental impact of my consumption patterns.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I see myself as an agent of change who can positively impact the environment.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I actively contribute to changing the narrative around travel by making more responsible decisions, such as choosing sustainable travel options.	<input type="checkbox"/>

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SUPLEMENTO AO DIPLOMA

A estrutura do Suplemento ao Diploma segue o modelo elaborado pela Comissão Europeia, pelo Conselho da Europa e pela UNESCO/CEPES. Tem por objetivo fornecer dados independentes e suficientes para melhorar a transparência internacional e o reconhecimento académico e profissional equitativo das qualificações (diplomas, graus, certificados, etc.). Destina-se a descrever a natureza, o nível, o contexto, o conteúdo e estatuto dos estudos realizados com êxito pelo titular do diploma a que este suplemento está apenso. São de excluir quaisquer juízos de valor, declarações de equivalência ou sugestões de reconhecimento. Devem ser preenchidas as oito secções, caso contrário, deve ser apresentada justificação.

1. INFORMAÇÃO SOBRE O TITULAR DA QUALIFICAÇÃO

1.1. APELIDO(S)

1.2. NOME(S) PRÓPRIO(S)

1.3. DATA DE NASCIMENTO (DIA/MÊS/ANO)

1.4. IDENTIFICAÇÃO DO ESTUDANTE E NÚMERO DO BI OU PASSAPORTE (SE ESTRANGEIRO)

2. INFORMAÇÕES QUE IDENTIFICAM A QUALIFICAÇÃO

2.1. DESIGNAÇÃO (NA LÍNGUA ORIGINAL) DA QUALIFICAÇÃO E TÍTULO QUE CONFERE (SE APLICÁVEL)

2.2. PRINCIPAL(AIS) ÁREA(S) DE ESTUDO DA QUALIFICAÇÃO

2.3. DESIGNAÇÃO (NA LÍNGUA ORIGINAL) E ESTATUTO DA INSTITUIÇÃO QUE EMITE O DIPLOMA OU CERTIFICADO

2.4. DESIGNAÇÃO E ESTATUTO DA INSTITUIÇÃO (SE DIFERENTE DE 2.3) QUE MINISTRA O CURSO (SE APLICÁVEL)

2.5. LÍNGUA(S) DE APRENDIZAGEM / AVALIAÇÃO (EXAME)

DIPLOMA SUPPLEMENT

This Diploma Supplement follows the model developed by the European Commission, Council of Europe and UNESCO/CEPES. The purpose of the supplement is to provide sufficient independent data to improve the international transparency and fair academic and professional recognition of qualifications (diplomas, degrees, certificates, etc.). It is designed to provide a description of the nature, level, content and status of the studies that were pursued and successfully completed by the individual named on the original qualification to which this supplement is appended. It should be free from any value judgements, equivalence statements or suggestions about recognition. Where information is not provided, an explanation should give the reason why.

1. INFORMATION IDENTIFYING THE HOLDER OF THE QUALIFICATION

1.1. FAMILY NAME(S)

1.2. GIVEN NAME(S)

1.3. DATE OF BIRTH (DAY/MONTH/YEAR)

1.4. STUDENT IDENTIFICATION (NUMBER OR CODE), ID CARD OR PASSPORT

2. INFORMATION IDENTIFYING THE QUALIFICATION

2.1. NAME (IN ORIGINAL LANGUAGE) OF QUALIFICATION AND (IF APPLICABLE) TITLE CONFERRED

2.2. MAIN FIELD(S) OF STUDY FOR THE QUALIFICATION

2.3. NAME (IN ORIGINAL LANGUAGE) AND STATUS OF AWARDING INSTITUTION

2.4. NAME (IN ORIGINAL LANGUAGE) AND STATUS OF INSTITUTION (IF DIFFERENT FROM 2.3) ADMINISTERING

2.5. LANGUAGE(S) OF INSTRUCTION / EXAMINATION

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3. INFORMAÇÕES SOBRE O NÍVEL DA QUALIFICAÇÃO

3.1. NÍVEL DA QUALIFICAÇÃO

Terceiro Ciclo de Estudos - Grau de Doutor - Nível 8 QEQ

3.2. DURAÇÃO OFICIAL DO PROGRAMA DE ESTUDOS

3 Anos- Tempo integral, 180 ECTS

3.3. REQUISITOS DE ACESSO

Podem candidatar-se ao 3º ciclo de estudos em Psicologia: a) Titulares do grau de mestre ou equivalente legal em Psicologia ou áreas afins; b) Titulares do grau de licenciado (correspondente a um mínimo de 300 ECTS) em Psicologia, em Ciências Sociais e Humanas ou áreas afins, detentores de um currículo escolar ou científico especialmente relevante que seja reconhecido pela Comissão Científica como atestando capacidade para a realização deste ciclo de estudos; c) Os detentores de um currículo escolar, científico ou profissional que seja reconhecido como atestando capacidade para a realização deste ciclo de estudos pela Comissão Científica.

4. INFORMAÇÃO SOBRE OS CONTEÚDOS E RESULTADOS OBTIDOS

4.1. REGIME DE ESTUDOS

Diurno - Tempo integral (2019/2020 - 2023/2024)
Diurno - Tempo parcial (2024/2025 - 2024/2025)

4.2. REQUISITOS DO PROGRAMA DE ESTUDOS

O 3º ciclo de estudos em Psicologia tem a duração de 6 semestres, correspondente a 180 ECTS, sendo constituído por uma componente curricular, com 60 ECTS (a que corresponde a atribuição de um diploma de curso de doutoramento não conferente de grau) e nos restantes semestres pela elaboração da tese, que inclui a realização de um seminário de investigação, e a sua defesa pública perante um júri a que corresponde 120 ECTS.

ÁREAS CIENTÍFICAS	CRÉDITOS	
	OBRIGATORIOS	OPTATIVAS
Psicologia	180	0
TOTAL	180	0

3. INFORMATIONS ON THE LEVEL OF THE QUALIFICATION

3.1. NATIONAL FRAMEWORK OF QUALIFICATIONS LEVEL AND AWARD TYPE

Third Cycle of Studies - Doutor (Doctor) Degree - Level 8 EQF

3.2. OFFICIAL LENGTH OF PROGRAMME

3 Years- Full Time, 180 ECTS

3.3. ACCESS REQUIREMENT(S)

May apply to the 3rd cycle of studies in Psychology: a) Holders of a master's degree or legal equivalent; b) Holders of a "licenciado" degree (corresponding to a minimum of 300 ECTS) in Psychology, in Social and Human Sciences or others, with an academic, scientific or professional curriculum, that is recognized as attesting the capacity to carry out this cycle of studies by the scientific committee of the cycle of studies; c) Holders of an academic, scientific or professional curriculum, recognized as attesting the capacity to carry out this cycle of studies by the scientific committee of the cycle of studies.

4. INFORMATION ON THE CONTENTS AND RESULTS GAINED

4.1. MODE OF STUDY

Full Time Day Course (2019/2020 - 2023/2024)
Part-Time Day Course (2024/2025 - 2024/2025)

4.2. PROGRAMME REQUIREMENTS

The 3rd cycle of studies in Psychology has a duration of six semesters, corresponding to 180 ECTS, which consists in a curricular component, with 60 ECTS (corresponding to the attribution of a non degree doctoral course) and in the remaining semesters, the preparation of the thesis, which includes conducting a research seminar, and his public defense before a jury, that corresponding to 120 ECTS credits.

SCIENTIFIC AREAS	CREDITS	
	COMPULSORY	OPTIONAL
Psychology	180	0
TOTAL	180	0

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5. INFORMAÇÃO SOBRE A FUNÇÃO DA QUALIFICAÇÃO

5.1. ACESSO AO NÍVEL DE ESTUDOS SUPERIOR (NÃO APLICÁVEL AO GRAU DE DOUTOR)

Não Aplicável

5.2. ESTATUTO PROFISSIONAL (SE APLICÁVEL)

Não Aplicável

5. INFORMATION ON THE FUNCTION OF THE QUALIFICATION

5.1. ACCESS TO FURTHER STUDY (NOT APPLICABLE TO DOCTOR DEGREE)

Not Applicable

5.2. PROFESSIONAL STATUS (IF APPLICABLE)

Not Applicable

6. INFORMAÇÃO COMPLEMENTAR

6.1. INFORMAÇÃO COMPLEMENTAR

Realização de um estágio em contexto de mobilidade Erasmus+, na Université Paris Naterre, entre 2022-09-01 e 2023-03-01.

6.2. OUTRAS FONTES DE INFORMAÇÃO

<http://www.fpce.up.pt>
<http://www.up.pt>
<http://www.dges.mctes.pt>
<http://www.naricportugal.pt>

6. ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

6.1. ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Internship under the Erasmus+ programme, at Université Paris Naterre, between 2022-09-01 and 2023-03-01.

6.2. FURTHER INFORMATION SOURCES

<http://www.fpce.up.pt>
<http://www.up.pt>
<http://www.dges.mctes.pt>
<http://www.naricportugal.pt>

REGIME	DURATION. 1	TIPO	TYPE. 2	ANO ACADÉMICO	ACADEMIC YEAR. 3	CLASSIFICAÇÃO LOCAL	LOCAL GRADE. 4	CLASSIFICAÇÃO ECTS	ECTS GRADE. 5	CRÉDITOS ECTS	ECTS CREDIT. 6
A. ANUAL	ANNUAL	OB. OBRIGATÓRIO	CORE			0-20 grading scale		ESCALA	GRADING SCALE	1 ANO ACADÉMICO	ACADEMIC YEAR = 60
1. 1ª SEMESTRE	1 ST SEMESTER	OP. OPCIONAL	ELECTIVE					A. 10%		1 SEMESTRE	SEMESTER = 30
2. 2ª SEMESTRE	2 ND SEMESTER							B. 25%			
								C. 30%			
								D. 25%			
								E. 10%			

7. AUTENTICAÇÃO DO SUPLEMENTO AO DIPLOMA

7.1. DATA.

2025/10/15

7.2. ASSINATURA.

[Redacted Signature]

7.3. CARGO.

Dirigente intermédio de 1º grau

7.4. SELO BRANCO OU CARIMBO

Todas as folhas do presente documento vão firmadas com o selo branco desta Instituição

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8. INFORMAÇÃO SOBRE O SISTEMA DE ENSINO SUPERIOR PORTUGUÊS

A Lei de Bases do Sistema Educativo (Lei nº 46/86, de 14 de Outubro, alterada pelas Leis n.os 115/97, de 19 de setembro, e 49/2005, de 30 de agosto, republicada e renumerada em anexo a esta última) estabelece o quadro geral do sistema educativo português. A educação escolar desenvolve-se em três níveis: os ensinos básico, secundário e superior. A **educação pré-escolar** destina-se às crianças com idade compreendida entre os 3 anos e a idade de ingresso no ensino básico e é universal para as crianças a partir dos 5 anos.

O **ensino básico** é universal, obrigatório e gratuito e compreende três ciclos sequenciais, sendo o 1.º de quatro anos, o 2.º de dois e o 3.º de três.

O **ensino secundário** compreende um ciclo de três anos (10.º, 11.º e 12.º anos de escolaridade) e deve ser concluído pelos jovens em idade escolar, cessando tal obrigatoriedade quando completarem 18 anos.

Quadro Nacional de Qualificações

Em 2009, foi aprovado o Quadro Nacional de Qualificações (QNQ), que abrange as qualificações formais de todos os subsistemas de educação e formação nacionais e as qualificações não formais obtidas da experiência profissional desenvolvidas no âmbito do Sistema Nacional de Qualificações. O QNQ estrutura-se em oito níveis de qualificação, adotando os níveis e os descritores do Quadro Europeu de Qualificações (EQF). O QNQ encontra-se referenciado ao EQF.

Organização do Ensino Superior

O ensino superior português compreende o ensino universitário e o ensino politécnico. O ensino universitário é ministrado em instituições universitárias públicas e privadas e o ensino politécnico em instituições de ensino superior politécnicas públicas e privadas. Os estabelecimentos de ensino privado obtêm reconhecimento prévio do Ministério com a tutela do Ensino Superior.

Grau de Licenciado

As instituições universitárias e politécnicas conferem o grau de licenciado. O ciclo de estudos conducente ao grau de licenciado no ensino politécnico tem uma duração normal de seis semestres curriculares, correspondentes a 180 créditos ECTS, ou, excepcionalmente, em casos abrangidos por normas jurídicas nacionais ou da União Europeia, uma duração normal de até sete ou oito semestres curriculares e uma formação de até 240 créditos ECTS.

O ciclo de estudos conducente ao grau de licenciado no ensino universitário tem 180 ou 240 créditos ECTS e uma duração normal compreendida entre seis e oito semestres curriculares. No 1.º ciclo de estudos, o grau de licenciado é conferido aos que, através da aprovação em todas as unidades curriculares que integram o plano de estudos do curso de licenciatura, tenham obtido o número de créditos fixado.

O grau de licenciado corresponde ao nível 6 do QNQ e do EQF.

Grau de Mestre

As instituições universitárias e politécnicas conferem o grau de mestre. O ciclo de estudos conducente ao grau de mestre tem 90 a 120 créditos ECTS e uma duração normal compreendida entre três e quatro semestres curriculares ou, excepcionalmente, em consequência de uma prática estável e consolidada internacionalmente, 60 créditos ECTS e uma duração de dois semestres.

No ensino politécnico, o ciclo de estudos conducente ao grau de mestre deve assegurar, predominantemente, a aquisição de uma especialização de natureza profissional. No ensino universitário o ciclo de estudos conducente ao grau de mestre deve assegurar, predominantemente, a aquisição de uma especialização de natureza académica com recurso à atividade de investigação ou que aprofunde competências profissionais.

8. INFORMATION ON THE PORTUGUESE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

The Framework Law on the Education System (Law nr. 46/86 of 14 October amended by Law nr. 115/97, dated 19 September and Law nr. 49/2005, dated 30 August, republished and renumbered in annex to the latter) establishes the general legal framework of the Education System. The educational system comprises three levels: basic, secondary and higher education. **Pre-school education** is for children aged between 3 and the age of entering basic education, and is universal for children from the age of 5.

Basic education is universal, compulsory and free and comprises three sequential cycles, the 1st lasting four years, the 2nd lasting two years, and the 3rd lasting three years.

Secondary education comprises a three-year cycle (corresponding to the 10th, 11th and 12th years of schooling) and must be completed by school-aged young people, an obligation that ceases at the age of 18.

National Qualification Framework

The National Qualification Framework (QNQ) was adopted in 2009. It comprises the formal qualifications of all education and training subsystems as well as the non-formal qualifications derived from professional experience within the framework of the National Qualification Framework. It includes eight levels of qualification, following the levels and descriptors of the European Qualification Framework (EQF). The QNQ is referenced to the EQF.

Higher Education Structure

Portuguese higher education includes university and polytechnic education. University education is provided by public and private university institutions while polytechnic education is provided by public and private non-university institutions. Private higher education institutions are subject to prior recognition by the competent Ministry.

Licenciado degree

Both university and polytechnic education institutions award the degree of *licenciado* (bachelor).

In polytechnic education, the cycle of studies leading to the degree of *licenciado* normally lasts six curricular semesters corresponding to 180 ECTS credits. In exceptional cases covered by national or European Union legislation, it may last up to seven or eight curricular semesters with up to 240 ECTS credits of student work.

In university education, the cycle of studies leading to the degree of *licenciado* has 180 or 240 ECTS credits, and normally lasts from six to eight curricular semesters.

In the 1st cycle of studies the degree of *licenciado* is awarded to those who pass all the course units of the *licenciatura* study programme, therefore obtaining the required number of credits.

The degree of *licenciado* corresponds to the level 6 of the QNQ and EQF.

Mestre degree

Both university and polytechnic education institutions award the degree of *mestre* (master). The cycle of studies leading to the degree of *mestre* ranges from 90 to 120 ECTS credits, and normally lasts from three to four curricular semesters. In exceptional circumstances resulting from a stable and consolidated practice in that specific field at international level, it may have 60 ECTS credits and last two semesters.

In polytechnic education, the cycle of studies leading to the *mestre* degree must ensure predominantly that the student acquires a professional specialization. In university education, the cycle of studies leading to the *mestre* degree must ensure mainly that the student acquires an academic specialization through research, innovation or development of professional competences.

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No ensino universitário o grau de mestre pode igualmente ser conferido após um ciclo de estudos integrado, com 300 a 360 créditos ECTS e uma duração normal compreendida entre 10 e 12 semestres curriculares, nos casos em que a duração para o acesso ao exercício de uma determinada atividade profissional seja fixada por normas legais da União Europeia ou resulte de uma prática estável e consolidada na União Europeia. Neste ciclo de estudos, é conferido o grau de licenciado aos que tenham realizado os 180 créditos ECTS correspondentes aos primeiros seis semestres curriculares.

No 2.º ciclo de Estudos, o grau de mestre é conferido aos que através da aprovação em todas as unidades curriculares que integram o plano de estudos do curso de mestrado e da aprovação no ato público de defesa da dissertação, do trabalho de projeto ou do relatório de estágio, tenham obtido o número de créditos fixado.

O grau de mestre corresponde ao nível 7 do QNQ e do EQF.

Grau de Doutor

O grau de doutor é conferido pelas universidades e pelos institutos universitários aos que tenham obtido aprovação nas unidades curriculares do curso de doutoramento, quando exista, e no ato público de defesa da tese, ou da compilação de um conjunto coerente e relevante de trabalhos de investigação, ou, no domínio das artes, por uma obra ou conjunto de obras ou realizações.

O grau de doutor corresponde ao nível 8 do QNQ e do EQF.

Cursos Técnicos Superiores Profissionais

O diploma de técnico superior profissional é conferido na sequência de um ciclo de estudos superior não conferente de grau académico designado Curso Técnico Superior Profissional (CTeSP), que corresponde a um ciclo de estudos curto ligado ao ciclo de estudos conducente ao grau de licenciado.

Os CTeSP são ministrados em instituições de ensino superior politécnico e em unidades orgânicas de ensino politécnico integradas em universidades.

Os CTeSP têm 120 créditos ECTS e uma duração de quatro semestres letivos, e integram componentes de formação geral e científica, técnica e de formação em contexto de trabalho.

Outros diplomas

No ensino superior podem ser atribuídos diplomas pela conclusão de parte de ciclos de estudos. Nestes casos, deve ser adotada uma denominação que não se confunda com a da obtenção final do grau académico correspondente.

Podem ainda ser atribuídos diplomas pela realização de outros cursos não conferentes de grau académico, alguns dos quais, como as pós-licenciaturas de especialização em Enfermagem ou os cursos de complemento de formação em Enfermagem ou em Ensino, se encontram regulamentados.

Condições de Acesso

O ingresso em cada instituição de ensino superior está sujeito a *numerus clausus*.

Ingresso no 1.º ciclo de estudos

Regime geral de acesso

Para se candidatarem ao 1.º ciclo de estudos conducente ao grau de licenciado através do regime geral, os estudantes nacionais e estrangeiros devem satisfazer as seguintes condições:

- Ter aprovação num curso de ensino secundário ou habilitação nacional ou estrangeira legalmente equivalente;

In university education, the *mestre* degree may also be awarded upon completion of an integrated cycle of studies, ranging from 300 to 360 ECTS credits and usually lasting 10 to 12 curricular semesters, in cases where the access to the practice of a certain professional activity depends on that length of time in accordance with European Union legal standards or results from a regular practice consolidated within the European Union. Within this cycle of studies, the degree of *licenciado* is awarded to those who have obtained 180 ECTS credits corresponding to the first six curricular semesters.

In the 2nd cycle of studies, the degree of *mestre* is awarded to those who have passed all the course units of the *mestrado* study programme, and who have publicly defended an original dissertation, project work or traineeship report, therefore obtaining the required number of credits.

The *mestre* degree corresponds to the level 7 of the QNQ and EQF.

Doutor degree

The *doutor* (doctor) degree is awarded by universities and university institutes to those who have passed all the course units of the *doutoramento* (doctorate) study programme, when applicable, and who have publicly defended an original thesis. It may also be awarded on account of a coherent and relevant set of research works or, in the field of the arts, on a work or a set of works or achievements.

The *doutor* degree corresponds to the level 8 of the QNQ and EQF.

Cursos Técnicos Superiores Profissionais

The *técnico superior profissional* diploma is awarded upon completion of a non-degree higher education cycle of studies entitled *curso técnico superior profissional* (CTeSP). It corresponds to a short cycle of studies within the cycle of studies leading to the *licenciado* degree. The CTeSP are provided by polytechnic higher education institutions as well as polytechnic organic units integrated in universities.

The CTeSP have 120 ECTS credits and normally last four curricular semesters including general, scientific and technical subjects, as well as a training period at the workplace.

Other diplomas

Higher education diplomas may also be awarded following the partial completion of a cycle of studies. In such cases, the chosen title must differ from the title of the final award of the applicable degree.

Diplomas may also be awarded for non-degree courses, some of which are regulated, e.g. postgraduate specialization courses in Nursing or supplementary courses in Nursing or Teaching.

Access conditions

Admission to higher education institutions is subject to *numerus clausus*.

Admission to the first cycle of studies

General regime

National and foreign students wishing to apply to the 1st cycle of studies leading to the *licenciado* degree through the general regime must fulfil the following conditions:

- Have successfully completed a secondary education course or a national or foreign qualification legally equivalent;
- Have taken the entrance exams required for the programme the student wishes to attend with a mark equal or higher than the minimum required (there are higher education institutions that accept foreign tests or exams);
- Have fulfilled the prerequisites (when applicable) of the programme the student wishes to attend.

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- Ter realizado as provas de ingresso exigidas para o curso a que se candidata com a classificação igual ou superior à mínima fixada (há instituições de ensino superior que aceitam provas ou exames estrangeiros);
- Satisfazer os pré-requisitos exigidos (se aplicável) para o curso a que se candidata.

A candidatura ao ensino superior público através do regime geral de acesso é feita anualmente através de um concurso nacional organizado pela Direção Geral do Ensino Superior.

A candidatura ao ensino superior privado através do regime geral de acesso é feita através de um concurso institucional organizado por cada instituição de ensino superior.

Regimes especiais de acesso

Para além do regime geral, existem regimes especiais de acesso ao ensino superior para atletas de alta competição, cidadãos portugueses em missão oficial no estrangeiro, funcionários nacionais e estrangeiros em missão diplomática, oficiais das Forças Armadas Portuguesas e bolseiros no quadro dos acordos de cooperação firmados pelo Estado Português.

A candidatura ao ensino superior através dos regimes especiais de acesso é feita anualmente através de um concurso nacional organizado pela Direção-Geral do Ensino Superior.

Concursos especiais

Para além do regime geral e dos regimes especiais, há concursos especiais para candidatos que reúnam condições habilitacionais específicas, possibilitando, em alguns casos, o ingresso no ensino superior a novos públicos numa lógica de aprendizagem ao longo da vida:

- Adultos maiores de 23 anos que tenham obtido aprovação em provas especialmente adequadas destinadas a avaliar a capacidade para a frequência do ensino superior;
- Titulares de outros cursos superiores, de diplomas de técnico superior profissional e de diplomas de especialização tecnológica;
- Titulares do grau de licenciado candidatos a Medicina;
- Estudantes internacionais.

É ainda possível, para estudantes que já tenham estado ou estejam matriculados e inscritos no ensino superior, o reingresso e a mudança de par instituição/curso.

A candidatura ao ensino superior através dos concursos especiais é feita através de concursos organizados por cada instituição de ensino superior.

Ingresso no 2.º ciclo de estudos

Podem candidatar-se ao ingresso no 2.º ciclo de estudos conducentes ao grau de **mestre**:

- Os titulares de grau de licenciado ou equivalente legal;
- Os titulares de um grau académico superior estrangeiro, que seja reconhecido como satisfazendo os objetivos do grau de licenciado pelo órgão científico competente da instituição de ensino superior onde pretendem ser admitidos;
- Os detentores de um currículo escolar, científico ou profissional, que seja reconhecido como atestando capacidade para realização deste ciclo de estudos pelo órgão científico competente da instituição de ensino superior onde pretendem ser admitidos.

As regras de admissão a este ciclo de estudos, as normas de candidatura e os critérios de seleção são da responsabilidade dos órgãos competentes de cada instituição de ensino superior.

An annual competition is held by the Directorate-General for Higher Education for admission to public higher education through the general regime.

Institutional competitions are held for admission to private higher education through the general regime.

Special conditions

Besides the regime geral (general regime), there are special conditions that apply to top-level athletes, Portuguese citizens on an official mission abroad, national or foreign diplomatic staff, permanent staff of the Portuguese Armed Forces, and scholarship holders within the framework of cooperation agreements agreed by Portugal.

An annual competition is held by the Directorate-General for Higher Education for admission to public higher education through the special conditions.

Special competitions

Besides the general regime and the special conditions, there are special competitions for applicants holding specific qualifications, thus opening higher education to new publics in a lifelong learning perspective, namely:

- Applicants over 23 years old who have passed special exams for assessing their capacity to accede to higher education;
- Holders of other higher education courses, *técnico superior profissional* diplomas, and *diploma de especialização tecnológica* (a post-secondary course certificate).
- Holders of the *licenciado* degree wishing to apply to Medicine.
- International students.

In addition, students who have been or are registered and enrolled in higher education are allowed to apply for readmission or to opt for another institution/programme pairing.

The special competitions for applying to higher education are held by higher education institutions.

Admission to the second cycle of studies

Those who meet the following conditions may apply to the 2nd cycle of studies leading to the **mestre** degree:

- Holders of the *licenciado* degree or legal equivalent;
- Holders of a foreign academic degree duly recognised as satisfying the objectives identical to the *licenciado* degree by the relevant scientific body of the higher education institution they wish to be admitted to;
- Holders of an academic, scientific or professional *curriculum vitae* that is recognized as attesting to the capacity to carry out this cycle of studies by the relevant scientific body of the higher education institution they wish to be admitted to.

The relevant bodies of each higher education institution are responsible for the regulations, application requirements and selection criteria for admission to this cycle of studies.

The access and admission to the integrated cycle of studies leading to the **mestre** degree are governed the norms applicable to the access and admission to the 1st cycle of studies leading to the *licenciado* degree.

Admission to the third cycle of studies

Those who meet the following conditions may apply to the 3rd cycle of studies leading to the **doutor** (doctor) degree:

- Holders of a *mestre* (master) degree or legal equivalent;

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O acesso e o ingresso no ciclo de estudos integrado conducente ao grau de mestre regem-se pelas normas aplicáveis ao acesso e ingresso no 1.º ciclo de estudos conducente ao grau de licenciado.

Ingresso no 3.º Ciclo de Estudos

Podem candidatar-se ao ingresso no 3.º ciclo de estudos conducentes ao grau de **doutor**:

- Os titulares de grau de mestre ou equivalente legal;
- Os titulares de grau de licenciado detentores de um currículo escolar ou científico especialmente relevante, que seja reconhecido como atestando capacidade para realização deste ciclo de estudos pelo órgão científico competente da universidade ou instituto universitário onde pretendem ser admitidos;
- Os detentores de um currículo escolar, científico ou profissional, que seja reconhecido como atestando capacidade para realização deste ciclo de estudos pelo órgão científico competente da universidade ou instituto universitário onde pretendem ser admitidos.

As regras de admissão a este ciclo de estudos, as normas de candidatura e os critérios de seleção são da responsabilidade dos órgãos competentes de cada universidade ou instituto universitário.

Ingresso no CTeSP

Podem candidatar-se a um CTeSP:

- Os titulares de um curso de ensino secundário ou de habilitação legalmente equivalente;
- Os que tenham sido aprovados nas provas especialmente adequadas destinadas a avaliar a capacidade para a frequência do ensino superior dos maiores de 23 anos, realizadas para o curso em causa;
- Os titulares de um diploma de especialização tecnológica, de um diploma de técnico superior profissional ou de um grau de ensino superior que pretendam a sua requalificação profissional.

As condições específicas para concorrer a cada curso técnico superior profissional são fixadas pelas respetivas instituições de ensino superior, em função da área em que o curso se insere.
Os concursos são realizados por cada instituição de ensino superior.

Sistema de classificação

Ao diploma de técnico superior profissional e aos graus de **licenciado** e **mestre** é atribuída uma classificação final expressa no intervalo 10-20 da escala numérica inteira de 0 a 20, bem como o seu equivalente na escala europeia de comparabilidade de classificações.

Ao grau académico de **doutor** é atribuída uma qualificação final nos termos fixados pelas normas regulamentadas aprovadas pela universidade ou instituto universitário que o atribui.

SE APLICÁVEL

Sistema de ensino superior português anterior

Cursos conferentes de grau

Antes da vigência da Lei n.º 49/2005, de 30 de agosto, da adoção de princípios reguladores para a criação do espaço europeu de ensino superior e do regime jurídico de graus académicos e diplomas do ensino superior que daí decorreu:

- No ensino universitário eram conferidos os graus de bacharel, licenciado, mestre e doutor;
- No ensino politécnico eram conferidos os graus de bacharel e licenciado;

- Holders of a *licenciado* degree who have a particularly relevant academic or scientific curriculum vitae that is recognised as attesting the capacity to carry out this cycle of studies by the relevant scientific body of the higher education institution they wish to be admitted to.

- Holders of an academic, scientific or professional curriculum vitae that is recognised as attesting the capacity to carry out this cycle of studies by the relevant scientific body of the higher education institution they wish to be admitted to.

The relevant bodies of each higher university or university institute are responsible for the regulations, application requirements and selection criteria for admission to this cycle of studies.

Admission to CTeSP

Those who meet the following conditions may apply to a CTeSP:

- Holders of a secondary education course or legal equivalent;
- Applicants aged over 23 who have passed the special exams for assessing their capacity to attend higher education required for a particular course;
- Holders of *diploma de especialização tecnológica*, *técnico superior professional diploma* or of a degree wishing to undergo reskilling.

The specific conditions to apply for a *técnico superior professional* course are set by higher education institutions, according to the field of the course.

The competitions are held by higher education institutions.

Classification system

The *técnico superior professional* diploma, as well as the **licenciado** and **mestre** degrees are assigned a 10-20 final classification on a numerical scale from 0 to 20, as well as its equivalent in the European scale of comparability of classifications.

The academic degree of **doutor** is assigned a final classification pursuant to the regulating standards approved by the awarding university or university institute.

WHERE APPLICABLE

Former higher education structure

Degree programmes

Prior to Law nr. 49/2005, dated 30 August, and ensuing adoption of the regulatory principles for the creation of the European Higher Education Area:

- The degrees of *bacharel*, *licenciado*, *mestre* and *doutor* were awarded in university education;

- The degrees of *bacharel* and *licenciado* were awarded in polytechnic education;

- Diploma to *licenciatura* programmes, organised in two stages, the first leading to the *bacharel* degree and the second to the *licenciado* degree, could be provided in polytechnic education. The first stage lasted six semesters and the second lasted two to four semesters;

- The programmes leading to the *bacharel* degree usually lasted three years, but under certain conditions could be one or two semesters shorter;

- The programmes leading to the *licenciado* degree usually lasted four years, but under certain conditions could one to four semesters longer;

- The programmes leading to the *mestre* degree had a maximum length of four semesters;

- Degree programmes were not assigned a given range of ECTS credits.

The former degrees remain valid as there is no matching mechanism or automatic conversion from the former to the current degrees.

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- No ensino politécnico podiam ser ministrados cursos bietápicos de licenciatura, organizados em dois ciclos, conduzindo o primeiro ao grau de bacharel e o segundo ao grau de licenciado. O 1.º ciclo do curso tinha a duração de seis semestres letivos e o 2.º ciclo uma duração de dois a quatro semestres letivos;
 - Os cursos conducentes ao grau de bacharel tinham uma duração normal de três anos, podendo, em casos especiais, ter uma duração inferior em um a dois semestres;
 - Os cursos conducentes ao grau de licenciado tinham uma duração normal de quatro anos, podendo, em casos especiais, ter a duração de mais um a quatro semestres;
 - Os cursos conducentes ao grau de mestre tinham uma duração máxima de quatro semestres;
 - Os cursos não se fixavam num intervalo de créditos ECTS determinado. Não foi previsto qualquer mecanismo de correspondência ou conversão automática dos graus anteriores para os atuais, mantendo os anteriores a sua validade.
- Aos graus e diplomas anteriores à implementação do Processo de Bolonha foram feitas as seguintes correspondências, no âmbito do QNQ:
- Os graus de bacharel e licenciado correspondem ao nível 6;
 - O grau de mestre corresponde ao nível 7;
 - O grau de doutor corresponde ao nível 8.

Cursos de Especialização Tecnológica

31 de dezembro de 2016, foi a data estabelecida como limite para os estabelecimentos de ensino superior poderem concluir cursos de ensino pós-secundário não superior, visando a formação profissional especializada, designados Cursos de Especialização Tecnológica (CET). Os CET têm 60 a 90 créditos ECTS e integram componentes de formação geral e científica, tecnológica e em contexto de trabalho. A conclusão de um CET conduz à atribuição de um diploma de especialização tecnológica e confere uma qualificação profissional do nível 4, de acordo com a estrutura de níveis de formação estabelecida na Decisão n.º 85/368/CEE, do Conselho, de 16 de julho, que corresponde ao nível 5 no âmbito do QNQ.

The degrees and diplomas prior to the Bologna Process implementation were given the following correspondences within the framework of the QNQ:

- The *bacharel* and *licenciado* degrees correspond to level 6;
- The master degree corresponds to level 7;
- The *doutor* degree corresponds to level 8.

Cursos de Especialização Tecnológica

Higher education institutions were given the deadline of 31 December 2016 to conclude the provision of post-secondary courses aimed at specialized professional training, entitled *Cursos de Especialização Tecnológica* (CET).

The CET range from 60 to 90 ECTS credits and include subjects in general, scientific and technical areas, as well as a training period at the workplace.

The completion of a CET implies a technological specialization certificate providing a level 4 professional qualification, in accordance with Council Decision 85/368/CEE of 16 July, which corresponds to a level 5 qualification within the framework of the QNQ.

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SISTEMA DE ENSINO SUPERIOR PORTUGUÊS

PORTUGUESE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

(1) QNQ - Quadro Nacional de Qualificações.

(2) QEQ - Quadro Europeu de Qualificações.

(3) Excetuam-se os casos em que seja indispensável, para o acesso ao exercício de determinada atividade profissional, uma formação compreendida entre 210 e 240 créditos ECTS.

(4) Excecionalmente, o ciclo de estudos conducente ao grau de mestre numa especialidade pode ter 60 créditos ECTS, em consequência de uma prática estável e consolidada internacionalmente nessa especialidade.

(5) O grau de mestre pode igualmente ser conferido após um ciclo de estudos integrado, para acesso ao exercício de determinada atividade profissional, quando a duração: a) seja fixada por normas legais da União Europeia; b) resulte de uma prática estável e consolidada na União Europeia. Nestes casos, o grau de licenciado é atribuído aos estudantes que tenham realizado 180 créditos ECTS (3 anos, 6 semestres).

(1) QNQ - National Qualifications Framework.

(2) QEQ - European Qualifications Framework.

(3) Except when in order to exercise a certain professional activity requiring education and training ranging between 210 and 240 ECTS.

(4) In exceptional circumstances, a cycle of studies leading to a *mestre* degree in a specialized field may have 60 credits, resulting from a stable and consolidated practice in that specific field at international level. 210 and 240 ECTS.

(5) A *mestre* degree may also be awarded following an integrated cycle of studies, for access to a professional activity, if the length: a) is established by European Union regulations; b) results from a regular and consolidated practice within the European Union; in such cases, a *licenciado* degree is awarded to students having obtained 180 ECTS (3 years, 6 semesters).

Glossary of terms

TERM	DEFINITION	SOURCE
<i>Attitude</i>	The motivators of performance, the basis for continued competent performance. They include values, aspirations and priorities.	Vuorikari, R., Kluzer, S. and Punie, Y., DigComp 2.2: The Digital Competence Framework for Citizens, EUR 31006 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-48882-8, doi:10.2760/115376, JRC128415.
<i>Competence</i>	A dynamic combination of the knowledge, skills and attitudes.	Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 June 2021 establishing the framework for achieving climate neutrality and amending Regulations (EC) No 401/2009 and (EU) 2018/1999 ('European Climate Law'), OJ L 243, 9th July 2021.
<i>Core skills</i>	Non-vocational, non-technical skills or competencies that are needed to perform at work and in society. They apply to work generally, rather than being specific to an occupation or industry. Core employability skills include the ability to work with others and in teams; the ability to solve problems and use technology; communications skills; and learning-to-learn skills. Core skills are also called generic skills, key competencies, key skills, portable skills, soft skills and transferable skills.	OECD, <i>OECD Skills Outlook 2023: Skills for a Resilient Green and Digital Transition</i> , OECD Publishing, Paris, 2023.
<i>Green skills</i>	Competences and knowledge necessary to the transition to a low-carbon economy, which can be general such as sustainable agriculture, soil protection, energy use and waste reduction, or more technical such as knowledge on renewable energy.	European Commission, <i>Erasmus+ Programme Guide</i> , 2026.
<i>Green skills and knowledge concepts</i>	The knowledge, abilities, values and attitudes needed to live in, develop and support a society which reduces the impact of human activity on the environment	ESCO Publications, <i>Green Skills and Knowledge Concepts: Labelling the ESCO classification</i> , 2022 (latest update: 2025).
<i>Green travel</i>	Travel that uses low emissions means of transport for at least half of the round trip, such as bus, train, bike, or car-pooling. Traveling by boat will be considered as green travel if combined with other	European Commission, <i>Erasmus+ Programme Guide</i> , 2026.

	low-emissions means of transport.	
<i>Informal learning</i>	Learning resulting from daily activities and experiences which is not organised or structured in terms of objectives, time or learning support; it may be unintentional from the learner’s perspective.	European Commission, <i>Erasmus+ Programme Guide</i> , 2026.
<i>Key competences</i>	The basic set of knowledge, skills and attitudes which all individuals need for personal fulfilment and development, employability, social inclusion, sustainable lifestyle, successful life in peaceful societies, health-conscious life management and active citizenship, as described in the Council Recommendation 2018/C 189/01 of 22 May 2018 on key competences for lifelong learning.	European Commission, <i>Erasmus+ Programme Guide</i> , 2026.
<i>Knowledge</i>	The outcome of the assimilation of information through learning. Knowledge is the body of facts, principles, theories and practices that is related to a field of work or study	ESCO Publications, <i>Green Skills and Knowledge Concepts: Labelling the ESCO classification</i> , 2022 (latest update: 2025).
<i>Learning mobility</i>	Moving physically to a country other than the country of residence in order to undertake study, training or non-formal or informal learning.	European Commission, <i>Erasmus+ Programme Guide</i> , 2026.
<i>Learning outcome</i>	Statements regarding what a learner knows, understands and is able to do on completion of a learning process, which are defined in terms of knowledge, skills and responsibility and autonomy; May be achieved through a variety of paths in formal, non-formal or informal settings, whether in national or international contexts.	Council Recommendation (2017/C 189/03) on the European Qualifications Framework (EQF) for lifelong learning.
<i>Non-formal learning</i>	Learning which takes place through planned learning activities where some form of learning support is present, but which is not part of the formal education and training system.	European Commission, <i>Erasmus+ Programme Guide</i> , 2026.
<i>Skill</i>	Ability to apply knowledge and use know-how to complete tasks and solve problems.	ESCO Publications, <i>Green Skills and Knowledge Concepts: Labelling the ESCO classification</i> , 2022 (latest update: 2025).
<i>Transversal</i>	Learned and proven abilities which are commonly seen as necessary or valuable for effective action in virtually any kind of work, learning or life activity. They are “transversal” because they are not exclusively related to any particular context (job, occupation, academic discipline, occupational sector, group of occupational sectors, etc.)	ESCO Publications, <i>Green Skills and Knowledge Concepts: Labelling the ESCO classification</i> , 2022 (latest update: 2025).

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UNESCO pillar	N.	Green competence	Description	Source
Learning to be = personal and family wellbeing / to develop one's personality and be able to act with ever greater autonomy, judgement and personal responsibility. In that connection, education must not disregard any aspect of a person's potential: memory, reasoning, aesthetic sense, physical capacities and communication skills.	1	Emotional regulation	<p><u>To recognise and regulate your mental and emotional state.</u> Even though green travel can be a very social experience, it also includes moments of solitude and independence, which in turn provide an opportunity for self-reflection and consciousness. Even more so, this competence reflects the ability to cope calmly, patiently and positively against stressful and unexpected scenarios, such as in the case of delays, changes to initial plans, lack of comfort, unforeseen situations (e.g., pickpockets, extra costs, loss of luggage), and feeling lost and in unfamiliar places.</p>	LifeComp
	2	Self-motivation	<p><u>To initiate and maintain goal-driven behaviours, be self-disciplined, and challenge yourself.</u> In some cases, sustainable travel is a more complex and demanding process to undertake, which shows commitment and courage. It can also include maintaining a positive attitude during a longer, more adventurous journey.</p>	LifeComp
	3	Planning	<p><u>To be self-reliant, take decisions, undertake responsibility, and manage your time efficiently.</u> Sustainable travel, especially when solo, requires a lot of prior planning and organisation, for example when booking tickets with different companies, scheduling layovers/waiting time, arranging luggage, mapping train/bus connections.</p>	WEF
	4	Responsibility	<p><u>To reliably fulfil obligations with integrity and proactiveness.</u> Students are more inclined to act proactively and responsibly, ask for and evaluate feedback, practice self-control, and be overcome with a profound and lasting feeling of pride due to their choice to travel sustainably.</p>	OECD
	5	Curiosity	<p><u>To enjoy a curious and inquisitive attitude towards new experiences and situations.</u> Sustainable travel is not the norm; students who embark on a green journey are interested in a different and unique experience.</p>	Erasmus Skills
	6	Environmental values	<p><u>To evaluate the level of agreement between human actions at an individual or societal level, and environmentalism.</u> Evidently, students choose to travel sustainably for their mobility are deeply concerned about the environment and want to uphold these values in practice in a meaningful and impactful way.</p>	GreenComp
	7	Interpersonal communication	<p><u>To effectively externalise and interpret information through verbal and non-verbal channels, and to possess active and empathetic listening skills.</u> Green travel invites students to use their communication and collaborative skills, in their native or a foreign tongue, for example to ask for advice or information from a help desk, a staff on board, or a fellow traveler.</p>	Erasmus Skills
Learning to be together = social cohesion, intercultural and international cooperation and peace / developing an understanding of other people and an appreciation of interdependence - carrying out joint projects and learning to manage conflicts - in a spirit of respect for the values of pluralism, mutual understanding and peace	8	Intercultural awareness	<p><u>To have an understanding of the characteristics of your own and other cultures.</u> Students who choose to travel sustainably can not only be more closely exposed to different people and cultures, but they also have an opportunity to get immersed in new environments and engage with the local community, especially if they stop along the way. This experience can put them in direct contact with other cultures, traditions, practices, and mentalities. A positive consequence is the greater respect for diversity.</p>	Erasmus Skills
	9	European values	<p><u>To see yourself as part of the European identity (solely or in addition/parallel to other identity groups).</u> The act of literally crossing borders by land brings students in touch with their European identity, for example when they travel visa and passport-free between countries that form part of the Schengen Area. They begin to appreciate and materialise the meaning of the freedom of movement.</p>	Erasmus Skills
Learning to do = Engagement in productive work and recreation / to acquire not only an occupational skill but also, more broadly, the competence to deal with many situations and work in teams, also in the context of young people's various social and work experiences which may be informal, as a result of the local or national context, or formal, involving courses, alternating study and work	10	Individual initiative	<p><u>To recognise the personal potential to proactively promote sustainability.</u> Students fully realise that green travel is an option for them, they feel certain and confident in pursuing it, and are actually willing to act according to this conviction.</p>	GreenComp
	11	Online search	<p><u>To search for and sort online data, information and content.</u> Especially in the preparation phase of the journey, students resort to online platforms, apps, and websites to research information (e.g., connections, stops, layovers, documentation). They also stay updated during the trip following the latest news and receiving notifications on their phone/via email.</p>	DigComp
	12	Evaluating data, information and digital content	<p>Students assess the validity/credibility of information online, compare their options, as well as try to identify greenwashing practices. Students explore new/innovative ways to search for and exchange information, e.g. via online forums, apps and platforms that are dedicated to green travel.</p>	DigComp
Learning to know = respecting and searching for knowledge and wisdom / combining a sufficiently broad general knowledge with the opportunity to work	13	Critical thinking	<p><u>To be able to solve problems and structure arguments based on analytical skills and logical reasoning.</u> This is a fundamental tool that enables students to evaluate the information at hand, make an informed judgment, open their horizons and challenge preconceived notions around</p>	LifeComp
Learning to transform oneself and society = active citizenship, futures thinking, responsible lifestyles, sharing of resources and adaptability	14	Adaptability/Flexibility	<p><u>To successfully and calmly answer and react to new situations and ambiguity.</u> Sustainable travel tends to be less straightforward and smoother than originally expected. This experience enables students to learn how to respond appropriately to new circumstances and resolve unforeseen problems. In a realistic scenario of adversity, creative thinking can help a student come up with a solution to overcome a problem during their journey; for example, when a train is cancelled, they can figure out an alternative route that could be even more convenient than the original plan.</p>	Erasmus Skills
	15	Evaluate environmental impact of personal behaviour	<p><u>To critically reflect on the different dimensions of your lifestyle and its impact on the natural environment.</u> Self-evident in the case of green travel that has a lower environmental impact than flying, potential of spillover effect in other aspects of lifestyle, such as food, clothing, waste.</p>	FSCQ
	16	Adopt ways to reduce the negative impact of consumption	<p><u>To take responsible and eco-conscious decisions that strive to decrease the harmful environmental impact of your consumption patterns.</u> Students are agents of positive change and actively contribute to changing the narrative around traveling by 'stepping up' and 'practicing what they preach'.</p>	FSCQ